

Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of some organic sulfides by tetrabutylammonium tribromide : A kinetic and mechanistic study[†]

Pradeep K. Sharma

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : drpkvs27@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The oxidation of thirty-four sulfides by tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) resulted in the formation of corresponding sulfoxides. The reaction is first order with respect to both TBATB and the sulfide. The solvent composition effect indicated that the rate of reaction increases with an increase in the polarity of the medium. The reaction failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. There is no effect of added benzyltrimethylammonium chloride or potassium bromide ions. Chlorobromate ion has been postulated as the reactive oxidizing species. The rates of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides were correlated with Charton's LDR equation. The rates of oxidation of the *ortho*-compounds showed excellent correlation with the LDRS equation. The oxidation of *meta*-compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. The reaction is subject to steric inhibition when an *ortho*-substituent is present. The oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides is subject to both polar and steric effects of the alkyl groups. The polar reaction constants are negative indicating an electron-deficient sulfur centre in the rate-determining step. A mechanism involving formation of a halogenosulfonium cation in the slow step has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, polyhalides, sulfides.

Introduction

Tetraalkylammonium polyhalides are widely used as halogenating reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. Recently, tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) has been used for the bromination of some selected organic substrates⁴. There are, however, only a few reports regarding their use as oxidizing and brominating agents in synthetic chemistry⁵. These compounds are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yields. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of polyhalides and many reports (including TBATB) have already emanated from our laboratory⁶. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by TBATB. In continuation of our earlier study, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of benzaldehyde and thirty-five monosubstituted benzaldehydes by TBATB in aqueous acetic acid as solvent. The major objective of this investigation was to study the structure-reactivity correlation for the substrate undergoing oxidation.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of organic sulfides by TBATB resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxides. The overall reaction may therefore, be represented as eq. (1).

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to TBATB. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to TBATB. Further, the first order rate coefficients did not vary with the initial concentration of TBATB. The order with respect to sulfide was also found to be one (Table 1). Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride : Addition of tetrabutylammonium chloride (TBACl) had no effect on rate of oxidation (Table 2).

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by TBATB at 298 K

10^3 [TBATB] (mol dm ⁻³)	[MeSPh] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	2.65	2.65
1.0	0.20	5.25	2.63
1.0	0.40	10.3	2.58
1.0	0.60	15.8	2.63
1.0	0.80	21.4	2.68
1.0	1.00	26.1	2.61
2.0	0.20	5.85	2.92
4.0	0.20	5.04	2.52
6.0	0.20	5.67	2.83
8.0	0.20	5.49	2.74
1.0	0.40 ^a	10.8 ^a	2.70

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfides by TBATB : A typical kinetic run.

Table 2. Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride or potassium bromide on the rate of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³	[Me-S-Ph] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³	Temp. = 298 K
10^3 [TBACl] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.5
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	26.1	25.2
	1.0	27.0
	2.0	26.6
	3.0	24.9
	4.0	26.0

Effect of solvent composition : The oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide was studied in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid and water. The rate of reaction increases as the polarity of the solvent is increased (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of solvent composition in the oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³	[Me-S-Ph] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³				Temp. = 298 K
% AcOH	25	40	50	60	72
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	135	50.4	26.1	12.6	4.68

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile/test for free radicals : The oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of a number of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides, alkyl phenyl sulfides, dialkyl sulfides and diphenyl sulfide were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 4). The log k_2 at different temperature is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for these oxidations.

Fig. 2. Oxidation of sulfides by TBATB : Effect of temperature.

Correlation between activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the thirty-four sulfides is linear

Table 4. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of organic sulfides by TBATB

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	9.81	26.1	71.1	180	71.5 ± 0.7	55 ± 2	87.7 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Me	19.8	46.5	130	315	68.0 ± 0.9	61 ± 3	86.1 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -OMe	41.4	104	261	621	66.3 ± 0.6	61 ± 2	84.3 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -F	10.8	28.8	80.1	207	72.7 ± 0.9	50 ± 3	87.4 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -Cl	7.11	19.6	55.5	146	74.4 ± 0.8	47 ± 3	88.4 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.78	2.48	7.74	22.5	83.1 ± 0.7	36 ± 2	93.5 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -COMe	1.17	5.13	15.3	43.1	79.5 ± 0.7	41 ± 2	91.7 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -COOMe	2.43	7.02	20.7	57.6	78.0 ± 0.9	44 ± 3	90.9 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -Br	7.02	19.3	54.7	144	74.4 ± 0.8	48 ± 3	88.4 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -NHAc	21.6	55.8	144	360	68.9 ± 0.7	57 ± 2	85.8 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -NH ₂	126	306	720	1580	61.8 ± 0.2	67 ± 1	81.6 ± 0.1
<i>m</i> -Me	17.1	43.9	115	279	68.6 ± 0.6	60 ± 2	86.4 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -OMe	19.8	49.5	126	297	66.4 ± 0.6	66 ± 2	86.1 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -Cl	3.80	10.5	29.6	77.4	74.2 ± 0.7	53 ± 2	89.9 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -Br	3.75	10.4	29.3	77.0	74.4 ± 0.7	53 ± 2	90.0 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -I	4.41	12.1	33.9	88.2	73.7 ± 0.7	54 ± 2	89.6 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.49	1.54	4.93	14.4	83.5 ± 0.8	38 ± 2	94.7 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	2.05	5.94	17.1	47.7	77.4 ± 0.8	47 ± 3	91.4 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -Me	4.41	12.6	36.9	99.0	76.7 ± 0.7	43 ± 2	89.5 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -OMe	11.7	30.6	84.6	216	71.8 ± 0.9	52 ± 3	87.2 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.27	0.92	3.15	9.90	89.1 ± 0.7	24 ± 2	96.0 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -COOMe	0.62	1.98	6.48	19.8	85.6 ± 0.9	29 ± 3	94.0 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -Cl	1.30	4.05	12.6	36.9	82.5 ± 0.7	33 ± 2	92.3 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -Br	0.98	3.06	9.99	29.7	84.4 ± 0.9	29 ± 3	93.0 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -I	0.76	2.43	8.01	24.3	85.7 ± 0.9	27 ± 3	93.5 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -NH ₂	34.2	87.3	223	531	67.2 ± 0.5	59 ± 1	84.7 ± 0.4
(ii) Alkyl phenyl sulfides							
Et	15.3	40.5	108	270	70.5 ± 0.6	55 ± 2	86.6 ± 0.5
Pr	9.72	27.0	77.4	207	75.3 ± 0.9	42 ± 3	87.6 ± 0.7
<i>i</i> -Pr	12.3	34.2	99.9	261	75.4 ± 0.8	39 ± 3	86.9 ± 0.7
<i>t</i> -Bu	3.15	9.72	30.6	81.9	80.6 ± 0.7	32 ± 2	90.1 ± 0.6
(iii) Other sulfide							
Me ₂ S	31.5	80.1	198	495	67.2 ± 0.9	60 ± 3	84.9 ± 0.7
Pr ₂ S	47.7	117	297	711	66.2 ± 0.8	60 ± 3	83.9 ± 0.6
Ph ₂ S	6.03	17.7	49.5	135	76.5 ± 0.8	41 ± 3	88.7 ± 0.7

($r = 0.9663$), indicating the operation of a compensation effect⁷. The value of the isokinetic temperature^{8,9} from this plot is 550 ± 26 K. However, according to Exner¹⁰, an isokinetic relationship between the calculated values of enthalpies and entropies of activation is often vitiated by the random experimental errors associated with them. Exner²⁴ has suggested an alternative method of testing the validity of isokinetic relationship. The plot of log

(rate) at 288 K is linearly related to log (rate) at 318 K (slope 0.8264 ± 0.0078 ; $r = 0.9986$) (Fig. 3). The value of the isokinetic temperature by Exner's method is 632 ± 33 K, which is in fair agreement with the value obtained earlier. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships. It also implies that all the compounds so correlated react by the same mechanism¹⁰.

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of sulfides by TBATB.

Reactivity of oxidizing species : We have earlier⁶ carried out some conductivity measurements to determine the nature of TBATB in aqueous acetic acid solution. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of TBATB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of TBATB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. We found that the conductivity increases sharply as the water content is initially increased but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. Therefore, TBATB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under our reaction, conditions as tetrabutylammonium and tribromide ions as eq. (2). No effect of added tetrabutylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (2) lies far towards the right. Similar results were obtained in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by TBATB⁶. Thus in the present reaction also the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to bromine and bromide ion [eq. (3)] and the value of the dissociation constant has been reported¹¹. However, in the presence of large excess of bromide ion, the following reaction will be suppressed. Thus in the present reaction the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

Solvent composition effect : The increase in the rate

constant with an increase in the polarity of the medium suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the dielectric constant is nonlinear. The solvent effect was analysed using Grunwald-Winstein equation¹².

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (4)$$

The plot of $\log k_2$ versus Y is linear ($r^2 = 0.9989$) with $m = 0.79 \pm 0.01$. The value of m suggests a transition state, which is more polar than the reactants. Thus considerable charge separation takes place in the transition state of the reaction.

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The data in Table 5 show that the oxidation of different sulfides follows the order of their nucleophilicity : $\text{Pr}_2\text{S} > \text{Me}_2\text{S} > \text{MeSPH} > \text{Ph}_2\text{S}$.

Aryl methyl sulfides : The effect of structure on reactivity has long been correlated in terms of the Hammett equation¹³ or with dual substituent-parameter equations^{14,15}. In the late 1980s, Charton¹⁶ introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities. In this work we have applied the LDR equation [eq. (5)] to the rate constants, k_2 .

$$\log k_2 = L \sigma_1 + D \sigma_d + R \sigma_e + h \quad (5)$$

Here, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when the active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (6).

$$\sigma_D = \eta \sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (6)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation.

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and Charton¹⁶, therefore, modified the LDR equation to generate the LDRS eq. (7).

$$\log k_2 = L \sigma_1 + D \sigma_d + R \sigma_e + S v + \eta \quad (7)$$

where v is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii¹⁷.

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and

para-substituted sulfides show an excellent correlation in terms of the LDR/LDRS equations (Table 5). All three series of aryl methyl sulfides meet the requirement of a minimum number of substituents for analysis by LDR and LDRS equations¹⁶. We have used the standard deviation (sd), the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), and Exner's¹⁷ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit.

the approach of the oxidizing species.

The percent contribution¹⁸ of the delocalized effect, P_D is given by following eq. (8).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100)/(|L| + |D|) \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the percent contribution of the steric parameter¹⁸ to the total effect of the substituent, P_S , was determined by using eq. (9).

Table 5. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of organic sulfides by TBATB

T (K)	-L	-D	-R	-S	η	R^2	sd	ψ	P_D	P_S
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	1.35	1.71	1.34	-	0.78	0.9998	0.005	0.02	38.9	-
298	1.25	1.62	1.38	-	0.85	0.9999	0.004	0.01	38.1	-
308	1.17	1.53	1.22	-	0.80	0.9998	0.004	0.02	39.0	-
318	1.08	1.44	1.12	-	0.78	0.9998	0.003	0.02	39.6	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	1.71	1.35	1.16	-	0.86	0.9999	0.001	0.01	32.0	-
298	1.62	1.26	1.08	-	0.86	0.9998	0.001	0.02	31.8	-
308	1.53	1.18	0.94	-	0.80	0.9998	0.004	0.02	32.3	-
318	1.44	1.08	0.85	-	0.79	0.9989	0.002	0.04	32.0	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	1.44	1.53	1.20	1.17	0.78	0.9998	0.006	0.02	36.7	21.9
298	1.35	1.44	1.17	1.09	0.81	0.9999	0.004	0.01	36.4	21.6
308	1.26	1.35	1.08	0.99	0.80	0.9998	0.002	0.02	36.6	21.2
318	1.47	1.26	1.00	0.91	0.79	0.9997	0.004	0.02	36.7	21.0

The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted phenyl methyl sulfides showed that the oxidation of *para*- and *ortho*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, L, D and R, are negative indicating an electron-deficient sulphur center in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , reflecting the electron-donating power of the substituent and its capacity to stabilize a cationic species.

The negative value of S indicates that the reaction is subject to steric hindrance by the *ortho*-substituent. This may be the steric hindrance of the *ortho*-substituents to

$$P_S = (|S| \times 100)/(|L| + |D| + |S|) \quad (9)$$

The values of P_D and P_S are also recorded in Table 5. The value of P_D for the oxidation of *para*-substituted sulfides is *ca.* 40% whereas the corresponding values for the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted sulfides are *ca.* 32 and 37% respectively. This shows that the balance of localization and delocalization effects is different for differently substituted sulfides. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the methylthio group from the plane of the benzene ring. The magnitude of the P_S value shows that the steric effect is significant in this reaction.

In earlier studies on the oxidations of sulfides, involving a direct oxygen transfer via an electrophilic attack on the sulfide-sulfur, the reaction constants were negative but of relatively small magnitude, e.g. by hydrogen peroxide (-1.13)¹⁹, periodate (-1.40)²⁰, permanganate (-1.52)²¹ and peroxydisulfate (-0.56)²². Large negative

observed solvent effect also supports the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Materials : Sulfides were either commercial products or prepared by known methods³⁰ and were purified by distillation under reduced pressure or crystallization. Their purity was checked by comparing their boiling or melting points with the literature values. TBATB was prepared by the reported method⁴. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 3 h and then fractionated.

Product analysis : Methyl phenyl sulfide (0.01 mol) and TBATB (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water (50 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand for *ca.* 20 h. Most of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water and extracted with chloroform (3 × 50 ml). The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate, the solvent was removed by evaporation and the residue was analysed by IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The spectra were identical with those of the corresponding sulfoxides. Peaks characteristic of the sulfide and sulfone could not be detected. In IR spectra, the product showed a strong and broad absorption at 1050 cm⁻¹. No band either at 1330 or 1135 cm⁻¹, characteristic of sulfones³¹ was seen. In NMR spectroscopy, studied in the case of Me₂S, the peak due to methyl protons shifted from 2.1 τ, in the sulfide, to 2.6 τ in the product. In the corresponding sulfone, the peak should have appeared at 3.0 τ³². Similar experiments were performed with the other sulfides also. In all cases, the products were the corresponding sulfoxides.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess (× 15 or greater) of the substrate over TBATB. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixtures, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (±0.1 K) and were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of TBATB at 394 nm for up to 80% reaction. Pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}, were evaluated from linear plots (*r* > 0.990) of log [TBATB] against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within ±3%. Simple and multivariate regression analy-

ses were carried out by the least squares method.

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